

INCLUSIVE AND INTEGRATED EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The principle of Inclusive Education was adopted at the “World Conference on Special Needs Education Access and Quality” (Salamanca Statement, Spain 1994). The statement solicits Government to give the highest priority for making education system Inclusive and adopt the principle Inclusive Education as a matter of policy. In India, NCERT joined hands with UNICEF and launched project - Integrated Education for Disabled children (PIED) in the year 1987, to strengthen the integration of learners with disabilities into regular school. In a recent year, the concept of Inclusive Education has been broadened to encompass not only students with disabilities but also all students who may be disadvantaged. Integration signifies the process of interaction of disabled children with normal children in the same educational setting. Inclusive Education broader and wider concept than Integrated Education as it includes all the students in mainstream. There are some differences between integrated and inclusive education, where inclusive education is found more beneficial than integrated education. The need of inclusive and integrated education is to provide opportunities to participate and develop relationships. The background of Inclusive and Integrated Education program has shown us, when the integrated education has come into picture and how the concepts of inclusive education has been broadened. There are many challenges like acceptance by peers, untrained teachers, poorly designed and equipped schools for implementing inclusive education. To overcome these challenges there are few measures like equal treatment of differently abled children as normal children, attitudinal changes of teachers, modification in the examination system are to be followed for the success of inclusive education. There is need to collaborate with education stakeholders and generate funds for moving from segregation to inclusion and also raising awareness of human rights to ensure that children with disabilities enjoy equal rights.

Keywords: Inclusion, Integration, Disabled, Mainstream, Challenges, Segregation.

Introduction

Every child deserves to receive a quality education. Education is a fundamental right and a social

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good. Majority of the disabled children are still left back without giving education in the country. The ‘SarvaShikshanaAbhiyana’ that is ‘Education for all not for selected’ as a flagship program of our nation under which ‘Inclusive Education’ is launched in 2001.

With the release of the Salamanca statement (UNESCO), a large number of developing countries reformulating their policies to promote the inclusion with disabilities into mainstream school.

Historically the educational systems have adopted an integrate model as an interim approach in the move towards education. The concept of Integrated Education arises as outcome of NPE1986, recommended to provide equal opportunity to all not only for access but also for success. In the integrated education model students with disabilities attend a regular emphasis. However, it is upon the student to fit themselves than the system to adapt to meet the education of student in India. Integrated education has been mainly students with mild disabilities who are easy to include into regular school programs. Government of India later planned for Inclusive Education for all children including disabilities and disadvantaged, so as to participate in the local mainstream school.

WHAT IS INTEGRATED AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION?

Integrated Education is the educational programme in which exceptional children attend classes with normal children on either a part- or full-time basis. It is placement of the disabled children in ordinary schools with some specialized educational help and services. Integration signifies the process of interaction of disabled children with normal children in the same educational setting. Integration also means mainstreaming.

Inclusive Education can be defined as “the process of increasing the participation of students in the cultures, curricula and communities of local mainstream school.” It includes all the students who are away from the education for any reasons like physically mentally challenged, economically, socially deprived or belonging to any caste, creed, gender etc. For inclusive education special planning can be done in mainstream education like special infrastructure specially designed classes, special curriculum

NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATED AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

- All children are able to be part of their community and develop a sense of belonging and become better prepared for life in the community as children and adults.
- It provides better opportunities for learning. Children with varying abilities are often better

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motivated when they learn in classes surrounded by other children.

- It encourages the involvement of parents in the education of their children and the activities of their local schools.
- It fosters a culture of respect and belonging. It also provides the opportunity to learn about and accept individual differences.
- It provides all children with opportunities to develop friendship with one another. Friendship provides role models and opportunities for growth.
- The growing body of research has shown that children do better academically when in inclusive setting and inclusion provides opportunities to develop relationships. Some of the benefits include-friendships, social skills, personal principles, comfort level with people and caring classroom environment.

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN INCLUSIVE AND INTEGRATED EDUCATION

INCLUSION

- The process of educating children in such a way so that it benefits all students and entails a clear participation.
- The focus is not on fitting into the main stream education, but improving participation of all students.
- Focuses on all students.
- To accommodate students’ needs, the school undergoes change.

INTEGRATION

- The process in which students with special needs are absorbed into the main stream education.
- Through an integrated approach, the students with special needs have to fit into main stream.
- Focuses on students with special needs.
- The child is made to accommodate its needs.

BACKGROUND OF INTEGRATED AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The Government of India is constitutionally committed to ensure the right of every child to

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basiceducation. The Government of India has created numerous policies around special education since the country’s independence in 1947. One of the earliest formal initiatives undertaken by the Government of India was the Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme of 1974(NCERT- 2011). The Kothari Commission (1966) which highlighted the importance of educating children with disabilities during the post- independence period (Pandey-2006). In 1980s the Ministry of Welfare, Government of India realized the crucial need of an institution to monitor and regulate the HRD programs in field of disability rehabilitation. Till 1990s 90% of India’s estimated 40 million children in the age group 4-16yrs with physical and mental disabilities are being excluded from mainstream education. NPE (1986) and the Programs of Action (1992) stress the need for integrating children with special needs with other groups. The Government of India implemented the District Primary Education Project (DPEP) in 1994-95. In late 90s (i.e. in 1997) the philosophy of Inclusive Education is added in DPEP. This programme laid special emphasis on the integration of children with mild to moderate disabilities in line with world trends and became one of the Government of India’s largest flagship programs of the time. NCF (2005) has laid down a clear concept of Inclusive Education. In 2005 the Ministry of HRD implemented a National Action Plan for the Inclusive Education of children and youth with disabilities. Furthermore, IEDC was revised and named ‘Inclusive Education of the Disabled at Secondary Stage’ (IEDSS).

Inclusive Education primarily focuses on mainstreaming students with disabilities in the general education settings and works on the principles of integration. In recent years, the concept of Inclusive Education has been broadened to encompass not only students with disabilities but also all students who may be disadvantaged. This broader understanding of curriculum has paved the way for developing the National Curriculum Framework (NCF-2005).

CHALLENGES OF TEACHER EDUCATION

The road to achieve Inclusive Education is a long varied one, on which challenges and opportunities will arise.

- Negative attitudes of student teachers towards Inclusive education.
- Less/no exposure of teacher trainees to children with special needs.
- Not making inclusive education subject as a compulsory subject in teacher education programme in some universities.
- Lack of practical training for teacher trainees to work in inclusive school.

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- Lack of training for teacher educators in teaching strategies and classroom management strategies in inclusive classroom.
- Most of the personnel in India are not trained to design and implement education programs for students with disabilities in regular schools.
- Most teacher training programs in India do not have a unit on disabilities (Myreddy and Narayan 2000).
- Majority of schools in India are poorly designed and few are equipped to meet the unique needs of students with disabilities.

FEW MEASURES TO PREPARE TEACHERS FOR INCLUSIVE SCHOOLS

Inclusive Education will be successful if these important features and practices are followed.

- Inclusive education should be a compulsory subject in the teacher education programme in all the universities.
- Teacher educators must be trained and equipped with inclusive school.
- Sufficient knowledge of classroom management strategies for inclusive classroom has to be included in the curriculum of B.Ed programme.
- Necessary school supplies such as audio learning or text books in braille should be made available.
- Suitable modification in the examination system has to be done.
- The reform of the curriculum should be made in parallel with the proper training for teachers regarding their knowledge of inclusion and its principles.
- Positive attitude in teacher educators and pre-service teachers towards inclusive education has to be developed.
- The B.Ed. curriculum must integrate theory with skill building through practicum.
- Teacher educators must be first trained with classroom management skills and teaching strategies.
- B.Ed curriculum need to be strengthened and modified to focus on practical part of inclusive education.
- Teacher trainees in teacher education have to be given more exposure to children with disabilities.
- Having teachers who have knowledge about different ways of teaching so that children with various abilities and strengths can learn together.

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Conclusion

It is an essential to build an inclusive society through an inclusive approach. A good inclusive education is one that allows all the students to participate in all aspects of class room equally. To meet the challenges the involvement and co-operation of educators, parents and community leaders is vital for the creation of better and more inclusive schools. The government of India is training to improve its education system focusing on the inclusive approach. The challenges can be overcome by raising awareness of human rights in communities and publicizing positive examples of disabled children and adults succeeding in inclusive education and in life beyond school. Training and support allow regular education teachers to implement inclusive education with ease and success.

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